

A REVIEW ON CHEBULAGIC ACID FROM *Terminalia* spp.: PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES, EXTRACTION TECHNIQUES AND PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES

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Abstract

Chebulagic acid is a distinctive hydrolyzable tannin belonging to the benzopyran tannin class that consists of a ¹C₄ glucopyranose center, where a chebuloyl group and a Hexahydroxydiphenic acid (HHDP) group occupies di-ester bridges at C-2,4 and C-3,5, respectively. It is also known as 3,6-(4,4',5,5',6,6'-hexahydroxy[1,1'-biphenyl]-2,2'-dicarboxylate)-1-(3,4,5-trihydroxybenzoate). In the Combretaceae family, chebulagic acid is the main constituent of the fruits of Terminalia Chebula, Terminalia citrina, and Terminalia catappa. Chebulagic acid can be extracted using Soxhlet extraction, column chromatography, and high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). It is active against Bacillus Cereus, and Staphylococcus aureus. It has been reported to consist of pharmacological activities, including the potent anti-inflammatory effect on Lipopolysaccharide (LPS), inhibited NF-kappaB activation by LPS, MAPK phosphorylation, anti-hyperglycemic effect and also has 5-LOX & COX-2 dual inhibition activity. This review covers the source of chebulagic acid, extraction methods, physico-chemical properties, along with its chemical structure and the pharmacological activities of chebulagic acid.

Keywords: Chebulagic acid, Terminalia Chebula, Terminalia Bellerica, HPLC, Astringency

Introduction

Chebulagic acid is a distinctive hydrolyzable tannin that belongs to the class of benzopyran tannin, which is commonly found in the fruits of *Terminalia chebula*, *Terminalia Bellerica*, *Terminalia citrina* and leaves of *Terminalia catappa*. It is a beige crystalline powder, insoluble in water but soluble in organic solvents along with ethanol solutions. It exhibits several pharmacological activities, namely inhibition of nuclear factor-κB (NFκB) activation and mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) phosphorylation in lipopolysaccharide (LPS) (Reddy and Redanna 2009), and inhibition of the activity of cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) and 5-lipoxygenase (5-LOX). It also consists of anti-inflammatory, anti-cancerous and antiarthritic, anti-infective effects, enhancing autophagy and anti-infective effects (Reddy et al. 2009).

Sources of chebulagic acid***Terminalia chebula***

Terminalia chebula fruit (Figure 1) is extensively used in folk medicine, Chinese herbal medicine, homeopathic, and Ayurveda medicine system. It is also used in other medicine systems due to the broad spectrum of pharmacological activities associated with the natural bioactive compounds present in this fruit. It shows several pharmacological activities like antioxidant, anti-cancer, antidiabetic, and antimicrobial. In addition, it contains various bioactive compounds such as tannins, chebulinic acid, chebulic acid, chebulagic acid, ellagic acid, gallic acid, and flavonoids (Manisha et al. 2020).

Figure 1a. Terminalia chebula fruits***Terminalia bellerica***

Terminalia bellerica, known as Bahera or Beleric, belongs to the Combretaceae family. It is a large deciduous tree common on lower hills in Southeast Asia. Tannins, glucoside, terpenoids, gallic acid, ellagic acid, ethyl gallate, chebulagic acid, galloyl glucose and belleric acid are the main active phytoconstituents of medicinal importance. The dried ripe fruit of *Terminalia Bellerica* (Figure 1b) has traditionally been used to treat diarrhea, cough, throat infections, and

fevers. In addition, the fruit decoction is used to treat dry cough, and the pulp of the fruit helps treat dysenteric-diarrhea, dropsy, piles, and leprosy (Narendra and Paul Khurana, 2017). Fruit and fruit extracts have various pharmacological activities, including antiulcer, antibacterial, anti-diabetic, analgesic, antioxidant, antifungal, and antihypertensive activity through in-vitro and in-vivo studies. *T. Bellerica* is one of the three ingredients of the well-known drug Triphala, used routinely in ayurvedic to treat a wide variety of illnesses (Narendra and Paul Khurana, 2017). *T. Bellerica* is also widely used in Unani, Siddha, and Chinese traditional medicine systems.

Figure 1b. Terminalia Bellerica fruits***Terminalia catappa***

Terminalia catappa is commonly found tree in Southeast Asia forests. The name was originated from the Latin word “terminalis,” referring to the leaves teeming at the shoots' ends. This tree grows well in tropical/subtropical climates and widely planted, grown for ornamental purposes and edible nuts. The nut kernel can be eaten raw and is a widely used herb in traditional medicine. The fresh *T. catappa* leaves juice is used to prepare medicinal lotion for scabies & leprosy and is orally consumed for stomach pain and headache. The leaves and fruits of *T. catappa* contain 1- degalloyl-eugenin, 2,3-(4,4',5,5',6,6'-hexahydroxy-diphenyl)-glucose, gentisic acid, chebulagic acid, corilagin, geraniin, granatin B, kaempferol, punicalagin, punicalin, quercetin, tercatin, tergalagin, terflavin A, and terflavin B, brevifolin-carboxylic-acid, beta-carotene, cyanidin-3-glucoside, ellagic-acid, gallic-acid, glucose, pentosans, tannin, all of which showing antibacterial activity, hepatoprotective activity, hypoglycemic activity, antioxidant activity, anti-inflammatory activity, angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitory activity, chemopreventive effect (Arumugam et al. 2015).

Terminalia citrina

Terminalia citrina, a deciduous tree, is of great ethnomedicinal significance in South Asia and Africa. It is broadly distributed

throughout India, Thailand, and Bangladesh's forests, and also known as Haleela Zard, belonging to the genus *Terminalia* and the family Combretaceae with approximately 200 species. Different parts of *T. citrina* are used to manage various diseases on a folklore basis. The fruits of *T. citrina* are used to manage chronic fever and loss of appetite. Fruits of *T. citrina* have also been used to treat asthma, boils, migraine, constipation, dental disorders, dizziness, hemorrhoids, anemia, eye diseases, traumatic cuts, infections, cardiac disorders, hepatomegaly, urolithiasis, diarrhea, and other digestive disorders. In addition, these fruits are anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and antipyretic remedies. The fruits are also employed as an anthelmintic in some Middle East regions. The fruits of *T. citrina* contain corilagin, punicalagin, 1,3,6-tri-O-galloyl-β-D-glucopyranose, chebulagic acid, and 1,2,3,4,6-Penta-O-galloyl-β-D-glucopyranose (Muhammad Furqan et al. 2016), all of which show, antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, analgesic and antipyretic activities (Muhammad Furqan et al. 2016).

Chemistry of chebulagic acid

The molecular formula of chebulagic acid is $C_{41}H_{30}O_{27}$. Chebulagic acid is a distinctive hydrolyzable tannin that belongs to the class of

benzopyran tannin. The hydrolyzable tannins are a group of plant polyphenols biosynthetically derived from galloyl esters with a polyalcohol core. These tannins contain hexahydroxydiphenoyl (HHDP) ester and its derivatives. Although biosynthesis of these tannins begins with simple C-C or C-O oxidative coupling of galloyl esters attached to glucose, various combinations of couplings both within a galloylglucose and between different galloylglucose units generate structural diversity of these metabolites.

Furthermore, hydrolyzable tannins like chebulagic acid are assumed to be generated by dehydrogenation and hydrolytic cleavage of one of the aromatic rings of the HHDP group. Their acyl groups spanning the oxygens at C-2 and C-4 of glucopyranose, which adopts 1C_4 or a related chair conformation, also seem to be biosynthesized from the HHDP group probably through its oxidative metabolite, the dehydrohexahydroxydiphenoyl (DHHDP) group. However, the biogenesis of the chebuloyl group, which spans O_2 and O_4 of glucose in chebulagic acid, remains obscure. Since its oxidation state is the same as that of the HHDP group, the chebuloyl group has been thought to be derived from the HHDP group by hydrolytic cleavage of its aromatic ring (Tanaka et al., 1996).

Figure 3 Structure of chebulagic acid (Liang-Tzung et al. 2011)

3.2 Physical and Chemical Properties of Chebulagic acid

Nomenclature: beta.-D-Glucopyranose,4-dihydro-3,7,8-trihydroxy-2-oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-4-yl) butanedioic acid, cyclic 3,6-(4,4',5,5',6,6'-hexahydroxy[1,1'-biphenyl]-2,2'-dicarboxylate)1-(3,4,5-trihydroxybenzoate)

Molecular formula: $C_{41}H_{30}O_{27}$

Molecular weight: 954.66 g/mol.

Characteristics: beige crystalline powder.

Solubility: chebulagic acid is insoluble in water, soluble in organic solvents including ethanol solutions.

Density: $2.1 \pm 0.1 \text{ g/cm}^3$

Boiling Point: 1610°C at 760 mmHg

pH Stability: Stable at 2.5 – 4.5

Storage: Protect from air and light, refrigerate or freeze (2-8°C)

Chemical Stability: Stable under normal temperatures and pressures.

Uses

Medicinal Uses

Chebulagic acid, a plant-derived hydrolyzable tannin, is mainly isolated from the fruits of *Terminalia chebula*, a popular folk and ayurvedic medicine in many African and Asian countries (Yang et al. 2013). Many raw materials containing hydrolyzable tannins have been used for treating different ailments. For example, in traditional Chinese medicine, the fruit of *Terminalia chebula* is commonly used for

treating infectious diseases (Yang et al. 2013). Chebulagic acid helps in toxin removal and reduction of body fat and acts as anti-aging compound improving the overall skin health as well. In previous studies, it showed profound pharmacological activities, including inhibition of cancer cell growth, antihypertensive, antioxidant, antibacterial activities immunosuppressive, hepatoprotective, enhancing autophagy, anti-infective effects, a potent alpha-glucosidase

inhibitor and also demonstrated the ability to inhibit herpes simplex virus 1, hepatitis C virus, and human immunodeficiency virus in vitro. (Kim et al. 2014; Liu et al. 2015; Yang et al. 2013). The dried fruits of *Terminalia chebula* contain an astringent matter originating from chebulagic acid.

Pharmacological Activities

Chebulagic acid extracted from some medicinal plants shows pharmacological activities, as shown in Table 1. Reddy et al. (2009) extracted chebulagic acid from the ethanolic extract of fruits of *T. Chebula* and investigated the enzyme inhibition activity of chebulagic acid of COX-LOX. Cyclooxygenase (COX) and 5-lipoxygenase (5-LOX) are the key enzymes responsible for inflammation. The results showed that chebulagic acid has a COX-LOX dual inhibition activity with IC₅₀ values of 15 ± 0.288, 0.92 ± 0.011, and 2.1 ± 0.057 μM for COX-1, COX-2, and 5-LOX (Reddy et al. 2009).

Yang et al. (2013) researched the antiviral activity of chebulagic acid against human enterovirus 71. Human enterovirus 71 is one of the primary causative agents of mouth, foot, and hand disease in children under six. Currently, there are no antiviral or vaccines available to treat EV71. Yang et al. (2013) demonstrated that the treatment with chebulagic acid reduces the viral cytopathic effect on rhabdomyosarcoma cells with IC₅₀ of 12.50 μg/mL. Furthermore, the

Table 1 Pharmacological activities of chebulagic acid

No	Pharmacological activity	Source	Type of extract	Tested platform	Reference
1	Anti-hyperglycemic effect	<i>T.chebula</i>	Ethanol-aqueous extract	Caco- Cell model SD-rats	Yi-Na et al., 2012
2	Inhibition of Angiogenesis	<i>T. chebula</i>	Ethanolic extract	Rat aortic rings Human umbilical vein endothelial cells	Athira et al., 2013
3	Antiviral Activity (Broadspectrum antivirals in vitro)	<i>T. chebula</i> , <i>T. catappa</i>	Ethanolic Extract	HSV-1 (Herpes Simplex virus type -1)	Liang-Tzung et al., 2011
4	Anti-inflammatory effects	<i>T. chebula</i> , <i>T. catappa</i>	Ethanolic Extract	LPS-stimulated RAW 264.7, a mouse macrophage cell line	Reddy and Redanna, 2009
5	Anti-proliferative potential	<i>T. chebula</i>	Ethanolic Extract	Retinoblastoma cells	Naresh et al., 2014
6	Antioxidant Activity	<i>T. chebula</i>	Ethanolic Extract	DPPH Assay	Sarmistha and Ramtej, 2015

Extraction of Chebulagic acid

Chebulagic acid can be extracted from *Terminalia ssp.* by using solvent extraction methods. However, the extraction of chebulagic acid is not done in a single protocol, and the procedures are widely varied. For example, in the high-speed counter-current chromatography system equipped with a preparative HPLC series and chromatographic column, successfully extracts and isolates the chebulagic acid from *Terminalia chebula* fruits. The 2-phase solvent system is composed of n-hexane-ethyl acetate-methanol-water (1:20:1:20 v/v). As a result, 33.20mg chebulagic acid with a purity of 95.3% was obtained in a single step from 300mg of crude extract (Han et al., 2006).

The details of extraction techniques, the yield of the resultant chebulagic acid, advantages and limitations of the extraction techniques are shown in Table 2. Traditionally, the commonly used method for extracting chebulagic acid is solvent extraction, where a liquid organic solvent passes through the grounded tissue and dissolves soluble compounds of the product matrix. Some examples of the traditional extraction methods are decoction, maceration, reflux extraction and Soxhlet extraction. Various solvents were tested and was observed that in the first extraction step, hexane or dichloromethane removes chlorophylls and lipids. In the second step the chebulagic acid will be extracted selectively. Then, depending on the polarity of chebulagic acid, other solvents were chosen, such as ethanol, potassium dihydrogen phosphate, orthophosphoric acid or

utilization of the chebulagic acid on mice induced with a lethal dose of EV71 was able to significantly reduce mortality and relieve clinical symptoms by the inhibition of viral replication. This showed that chebulagic acid can be considered as potential therapeutic agent to control enterovirus 71.

In recent research for an effective inhibitor of ferroptosis, a cell death pathway, Yang et al. (2021) selected chebulagic acid for the study. The ferroptosis inhibition by chebulagic acid was determined using an erastin-treated bone marrow-derived mesenchymal stem cells (bmMSCs) model and compared with ferrostatin-1 (Fer-1). The UHPLC-ESI-Q-TOF-MS analysis suggested that when treated with 16-(2-(14-carboxytetradecyl)-2-ethyl-4,4-dimethyl-3-oxazolidinyloxy free radicals, Fer-1 generated dimeric products, whereas the chebulagic acid had not generated any compounds, this showed that chebulagic acid can act as a natural ferroptosis inhibitor (Yang et al. 2021). Chebulagic acid ferroptosis inhibition is mediated by regular antioxidant pathways (ROS scavenging and iron chelation) rather than the redox-based catalytic recycling pathway exhibited by Fer-1. Therefore, chebulagic acid is safer than Fer-1 concerning its inhibitory pathways and dimeric products (Yang et al. 2021).

methanol. However, using solvents such as methanol generates residues, which are harmful to the environment and ultimately affecting animal and human health. The extraction methods such as soxhlet, maceration, reflux, sonication, capillary electrophoresis, column chromatography, and high-performance liquid chromatography produce 57.89 to 255.71 mg/g of chebulagic acid (Table 2).

Supercritical fluid extraction is often used for the extraction of non-polar compounds (Liu et al. 2011). According to Liu et al. (2011), it is an alternative technique to conventional extraction techniques, such as soxhlet and others, owing to its advantages to low density and viscosity of supercritical carbon dioxide as high diffusivity. Moreover, carbon dioxide is non-flammable and "green," thus, it has no harmful impact on the environment (Liu et al. (2011). However, CO₂ is a non-polar molecule, while chebulagic acid is a polar compound, therefore, polar co-solvents such as ethanol and aqueous mixtures increases the solubility of chebulagic acid and the extraction efficiency (Mrudula et al., 2022). Various factors are involved in the supercritical fluid extraction, such as the moisture content of raw material, nature of the solvent and co-solvent, extraction time, flow rate, particle size, and especially pressure and temperature (Mrudula et al., 2022). The chebulagic acid extracted using the supercritical fluid extraction with ethanol as a modifier is 799.2 mg/g (Mrudula et al., 2022) (Table 2).

Table 2 Extraction, the yield of chebulagic acid, advantages, and limitations

No	Extraction method	Solvent used	Yield (mg/g)	Advantages	Limitations	References
1	Solvent extraction	Methanol	255.71	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Several extractions can be performed in parallel. 2. Required little training 3. Can extract more sample mass than other methods 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A large amount of extractant waste 2. Extraction is limited extractant and difficult to automate 3. Temperature gradient heating 4. Hazardous and flammable liquid organic solvent 5. Potential toxic emissions during extraction 6. Costly and high purity solvents are required 	Jibrin et al. 2014
2	Reflux Extraction	Methanol	33.20	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Suitable for low moisture foods application 2. Suitable for application to foods containing volatile oils 3. Equipment is economical, easy to install, handle and use 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Destructive 2. Relatively time-consuming 3. Involves the use of flammable solvents 	Han et al. 2006
3	Sonication method	Potassium dihydrogen phosphate, Orthophosphoric acid	108.00	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Easy to handle, safe 2. Moderate use of solvent 3. Reproducible 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Required filtration step 2. Possible degradation of compounds at high frequencies 	Pawar et al. 2009
4	Maceration method, Column Chromatography	Water and methanol	134.77	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Required little or no training 2. Economical 3. Easy to operate and handle 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Longer extraction time 2. A large amount of extractant waste 3. Hazardous and flammable liquid organic solvent usage 4. Potential toxic emissions during extraction 	Tushar et al. 2015
5	High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) method	Methanol	57.89	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Automated operation 2. Rapid and precise quantitative analysis 3. Quantitative sample recovery 4. Amenable to diverse samples 5. High-sensitive detection 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Less separation efficiency than capillary gas chromatography (GC) 2. More difficult for novices 3. No universal detector 	Lih-Jeng et al. 2004
6	Capillary Electrophoresis method	Methanol	59.31	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Easy and predictable selectivity 2. Small sample sizes 3. Fast separations 4. Can be automated 5. Easily coupled to MS 6. Offers new selectivity, an alternative to HPLC 7. High separation efficiency 8. Quantitation (linear) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reproducibility problems 2. Cannot do preparative scale separations 3. Difficulties in detection 4. Long analysis time 	Lih-Jeng et al. 2004

7	Supercritical fluid extraction with modifier	50% ethanol and carbon dioxide	799.2	1. Elimination of organic solvent 2. Rapid extraction 3. Suitable for the extraction and purification of compounds with low volatility 4. Thermal degradation 5. Solvent separation from the extract 6. Continuous process 7. Economical 8. Easy solvent recovery 9. Efficient	1. Prolong time 2. Modeling is inaccurate 3. Expensive 4. Consistency and reproducibility may vary in continuous process flow.	Mrudula et al. 2022
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Conclusion

Terminalia species have been widely used for their medicinal properties. Chebulagic acid is a hydrolyzable tannin found in the fruits and leaves of *Terminalia chebula*, *Terminalia Bellerica*, *Terminalia citrina*, and *Terminalia catappa*. It is extracted from medicinal herbs using column chromatography, soxhlet extractor, and high-pressure liquid chromatography. It shows pharmacological activities like antioxidant, antimicrobial activities, antifungal, antibacterial activities, antiviral activity, anti-inflammatory effects, anti-hyperglycemic effect, inhibition of nuclear factor- κ B (NF κ B) activation and mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) phosphorylation in lipopolysaccharide (LPS), and blocks the activity of cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) and 5-lipoxygenase (5-LOX), anti-proliferative potential, and inhibition of angiogenesis in addition to removal of toxins and unwanted fat from the body.

Future Prospects

Evidence indicates that chebulagic acid may be protective against some chronic diseases. Although recent decades have witnessed an increased understanding of some of the potential mechanisms of chebulagic acid, research efforts should attempt to shed light on the action mechanisms at the cellular and molecular levels. The research will be essential for Nutrigenomics (effects of nutrients on the proteome, metabolome, and genome) and nutrigenetics (effects of genetic variation on the interaction between disease and diet). Further research should be conducted on the extraction of chebulagic acid to attain higher yield and purity. As the efficiency of chebulagic acid and its various pharmacological activities have been reported, further research needs to be conducted on other food and pharmacological applications.

References

1. Arumugam V.A., Natarajan D, and Pannerselvam P.K., 2015, 'An updated review of *Terminalia catappa*,' Pharmacogn Review, Vol. 9, no. 18, pp. 93–98.
2. Athira A.P., Helen A, Saja K, Reddanna P, and Sudhakaran P.R., 2013, 'Inhibition of Angiogenesis In Vitro by Chebulagic Acid: A COX-LOX Dual Inhibitor,' International Journal of Vascular Medicine, pp. 843-897.
3. Han Q, Song J, Qiao C, Wong L, Xu H, 2006, Preparation isolation of hydrolyzable tannins chebulagic acid and chebulinic acid from *Terminalia Chebula* by High-Speed Counter-Chromatography. Journal of Separation Science, Vol. 29, no. 11, pp. 1653-1657.
4. Haslam E, Uddin M, 1967, 'Gallotannins. Part XV. Some observations on the structures of chebulinic acid and its derivatives.' J. Chem. Soc., pp. 2381–2384.

5. Kim H.J., Kim J, Kang K.S., Lee K.T., and Yang H.O., 2014, 'Neuroprotective Effect of Chebulagic Acid via Autophagy Induction in SH-SY5Y Cells', Biomolecules & Therapeutics, Vol. 22, no. 4, pp. 275-281.
6. Liang-Tzung L, Ting-Ying C, Chueh-Yao C, Ryan S.N., Bruce G, Craig M, Ta-Chen L, Guey-Horng W, Chun-Ching L, and Christopher D.R., 2011, 'Hydrolyzable Tannins (Chebulagic Acid and Punicalagin) Target Viral Glycoprotein-Glycosaminoglycan Interactions to Inhibit Herpes Simplex Virus 1 Entry and Cell-to-Cell Spread', Journal of Virology, Vol. 85, no. 9, pp. 4386–4398.
7. Lih-Jeng J, Shuenn-Jyi S and Ta-Chen L, 2004, 'Determination of hydrolyzable tannins in the fruit of *Terminalia chebula* Retz. by high-performance liquid chromatography and capillary electrophoresis', Journal of Separation Science, Vol. 27, no. 9, pp. 718-24
8. Liu Y, Bao L, Xuan L, Song B, Lin L, and Han H, 2015, 'Chebulagic acid inhibits the LPS-induced expression of TNF- α and IL-1 β in endothelial cells by suppressing MAPK activation', Experimental and Therapeutic Medicine, Vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 263-268.
9. Manisha N, Abhay Mishra P, Anjana A.D., Amina Ibrahim D, Md. Mahadi Hassan, Achyut A, Tarun B, Hari Prasad D, 2020, 'Fruits of *Terminalia chebula* Retz.: A review on traditional uses, bioactive chemical constituents, and pharmacological activities', Phytotherapy Research, Vol. 34, pp. 2518–2533.
10. Mrudula G, Chow S.C., Siow L.F., 2022, 'Supercritical fluid extraction of chebulagic acid from *Terminalia bellirica* fruits (Baheda),' Journal of Food Processing and Preservation, pp. 1-10
11. Muhammad Furqan A, Ammara S, Ali S, Bushra A, Maaz Bin N, Sohaib P, Moosa R, Hira I, Shoaib A, Maryam S, Sajid A, Zeeshan A, Syed Saeed U.H., 2016, 'Genotoxic and Cytotoxic Action Potential of *Terminalia Citrina*, A Medicinal Plant of Ethnopharmacological Significance,' EXCLI Journal, pp. 589-598.
12. Narendra K and Paul Khurana S.M., 2018, 'Phytochemistry and medicinal potential of the *Terminalia bellerica* (Bahera),' Indian Journal of Natural Products and Resources, Vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 97-107.
13. Naresh K, Gangappa D, Geetika G, and Roy K., 2015, 'Chebulagic acid from *Terminalia chebula* causes G1 arrest, inhibits NF κ B and induces apoptosis in retinoblastoma cells',

- BMC Complementary and Alternative Medicine, Vol. 14, pp. 319-329.
14. **Okuda T, Hatano T, Nitta H, Fujii R, 1980**, 'Hydrolysable tannins having enantiomeric dehydrohexahydroxydiphenoyl group: Revised structure of terchebin and structure of granatin B.' *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 21, pp. 4361–4364.
 15. **Pawar V, Lahorkar P, and Anantha Narayana D.B., 2009**, 'Development of a RP-HPLC method for analysis of Triphala curna and its applicability to test variations in Triphala curna preparations', *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Science*, Vol. 71, no. 4, pp. 382-386.
 16. **Reddy D. B., Reddy T. C. M., Jyotsna G., Satish S, Nalini P, Lakshmipathi V., and Reddanna P, 2009**, 'Chebulagic acid, a COX-LOX dual inhibitor isolated from the fruits of Terminalia chebula Retz., induces apoptosis in COLO-205 cell line', *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, Vol. 124, no. 3, pp. 506–512.
 17. **Reddy D.B. and Reddanna P, 2009**, 'Chebulagic acid (CA) attenuate LPS-induced inflammation by suppressing NF-κB and MAPK activation in RAW 264.7 macrophages', *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications*, Vol. 381, no. 1, pp. 112–117.
 18. **Sarmistha S and Ramtej J.V., 2015**, 'Antioxidant activity of polyphenolic extract of Terminalia chebula Retzius fruits,' *Journal of Taibah Univ Science*, Vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 805-812.
 19. **Schmidt O.T., Demmler K, Bittermann H, 1957**, 'Über natürliche gerbstoffe XXVII. Neochebulinsäure und 1.3.6-trigalloyl-glucose.' *Liebigs Ann. Chem.*, 609, pp. 192–199.
 20. **Schmidt O.T., Schulz J, Fiesser H, 1967**, 'Über natürliche gerbstoffe XXVIII. Die gerbstoffe der myrobalanen.' *Liebigs Ann. Chem.*, 706, pp. 187–197. (In German)
 21. **Tanaka T, Kouno I, and Nonaka G.I., 1996**, 'Glutathione-mediated conversion of the ellagitannin geraniin into chebulagic acid,' *Chemical and Pharmaceutical Bulletin*, vol. 44, no. 1, pp. 34–40.
 22. **Tushar D, Sonal S, and Satyanshu K, 2015**, 'A Validated High-Performance Liquid Chromatography Method for Determination of Tannin-Related Marker Constituents Gallic Acid, Corilagin, Chebulagic Acid, Ellagic Acid, and Chebulinic Acid in Four Terminalia Species from India', *Journal of Chromatographic Science*, Vol. 53, no. 4, pp. 625–632,
 23. **Tushar Kumar D, Rajendra Y, and Satyanshu K, 2017**, 'Chemical Investigation of Phenolic constituents of two important medicinal plants: Terminalia Chebula and Saraca Asoca,' Doctor of Philosophy, Department of Chemistry, Shri Jagdishprasad Jhambarmal Tiberwala University, Rajasthan, India, pp. 173-197.
 24. **Yamada H, Wakamori S, Hirokane T, Ikeuchi K, Matsumoto S, 2018**, 'Structural Revisions in Natural Ellagitannins.' *Molecules*, 23(8):1901.
 25. **Yang L, Liu Y, Zhang W, Hua Y, Chen B, Wu Q, Chen D, Liu S, Li X, 2021**, 'Ferroptosis-Inhibitory Difference between Chebulagic Acid and Chebulinic Acid Indicates Beneficial Role of HHDP.' *Molecules*, 15;26(14):4300.
 26. **Yang Y, Xiu J, Liu J, Zhang L, Li X, Xu Y, Qin C and Zhang L, 2013**, 'Chebulagic Acid, a Hydrolyzable Tannin, Exhibited Antiviral Activity in Vitro and in Vivo against Human Enterovirus 71', *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, Vol. 14, no. 5, pp. 9618-9627.
 27. **Yi-Na H, Dong-Dong Z, Bo G, Kai Z, Rui-Xue Z, Yan Z, Wang-Jun X, Li-Rong J, and Hong G, 2012**, 'Anti-Hyperglycemic Effect of Chebulagic Acid from the Fruits of Terminalia Chebula Retz.' *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, pp. 6320-6333.